

Features of Organizing the Distance Education System in Universities

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Abstract: *This article highlights the specifics of the introduction of distance education, in particular, the advantages and disadvantages of distance education. The existing opportunities in the system and the prospects for the introduction of distance learning are reflected in the article.*

Keywords: *information technology, online textbooks, education system, distance education, virtual environment, monitoring, external education, economic achievements, technical equipment.*

Today, development is developing and changing very fast. Almost every minute, changes, updates and unexpected events are happening in different parts of our planet. Every day we live under a strong stream of news. A person cannot function normally without the influence of information.

The development of information technologies has had a direct impact on all areas, in particular, on the implementation of the distance education system in various educational institutions. Distance education is a relatively young method of education, and such education began to appear in practice with the advent of the Internet. In this method of teaching, the student can acquire knowledge using online textbooks, video recordings of classes and other virtual educational materials. In fact, there is no doubt that the live interaction between the student and the teacher is very important and very effective in learning. But in certain situations, it is impossible to provide education to a student without distance education. Remote education is very effective in the following situations:

- those who want to get a second higher or additional education, improve their qualifications and retrain;
- heads of regional authorities and management;
- young people who could not get education due to the limitations of the traditional education system;
- employees of companies and enterprises who want to raise their information status to the level of modern requirements;
- listeners who want to receive second parallel information;
- residents of underdeveloped regions far from the center;
- persons with limited freedom of movement;
- persons with physical disabilities;
- persons in military service, etc.

All of the above reasons, in a good way, point to the fact that distance education should be present in every educational institution at one level or another, because the introduction of such a large-scale inclusion makes it possible for students with disabilities to study from anywhere. . Distance education has methodical, economic, social advantages and advantages, as well as disadvantages and disadvantages. Methodological achievements and advantages include: Individual approach and

personalization of the educational process. The distance learning schedule can be adapted to each student and can be changed depending on the circumstances. At the same time, the curriculum can be flexible and take into account the characteristics of the student, such as the speed of information perception, initial level of preparation, learning motivation, inclination to one or another form of material perception. Improving the quality of education. We can say that this opinion is controversial, because we all know that traditional forms of teaching are more effective. At the same time, no one can deny that the development of the Internet has made it easier for everyone to access a large amount of educational materials. This is also one of the manifestations of technological progress. Expanding the boundaries and reducing the costs of the components of the educational process. Some students can save more than an hour of commuting time every day, and some can even study in an educational institution located in another part of the country. Replacing printed educational materials with electronic ones can save a lot of money. Pedagogical experience maintenance. In unique authoring courses, for example, when working with gifted students, if the lectures of the teachers are recorded and saved, they can be used many times again. Economic benefits and advantages may include:

- Unlimited distance learning. The distance between the teacher and students is not important.
- It does not interfere with the work process. The student receives education in a state that cannot be separated from work.

- Increasing the number of students. The number of students of an educational institution that fully uses distance education technologies can increase by 2-3 times. Social achievements and benefits may include:

- Lack of division into social groups. Those who receive second higher or additional education in a distance education course, who wish to improve their qualifications and retrain; students who want to get second parallel education; residents of less developed regions far from the center; persons with physical disabilities; persons in army service; persons with limited freedom of movement; and others may attend.

- No age restrictions. The age restrictions of those involved in the study are excluded. But it should be said that there are negative aspects of distance education. We can include the following:

- Lack of trust in electronic learning and communication processes. For this reason, students mainly want to study in regular (full-time and extramural) types of education, not in virtual education.

- Absence of state distance education standards and, as a result, not issuing a state-copy diploma. For this reason, many distance education courses graduates only receive a certificate or certificate of completion of this course.

- Connection with virtual environment and technical support. Distance education refers to the availability of the Internet, the cost of its use, the speed and availability of services, the availability and operation of special communication techniques. The issue of introducing distance education should be considered from three sides.

- Social. Everything is simple here, today students actively use social networks, forums and chats.

- Technician. In terms of technical equipment, educational institutions are doing a good job in this regard, there are enough computers, and there is an opportunity to connect to the Internet. But not every student has a computer at home. Another problem is that students are not always able to independently organize, for example, a video conference. There are problems with the quality of the Internet in remote areas, where it is impossible to ensure the stability of distance education.

- methodical. The main contradiction is that the use of distance education makes sense only if it improves the quality of education in general, but it is difficult for many people to do this because of the lack of necessary experience and development. That is, any program for the introduction of distance education should take into account all these aspects. The process itself can be divided into five stages:
 1. Creation of a creative team of teachers responsible for distance education in an educational institution.
 2. Training of this group in special training courses.
 3. Preparation of a base of educational material used by students in the educational process and for independent reinforcement of what they have learned.

4. Comprehensive study of a distance learning system such as Moodle.
5. For this, independently develop distance courses or attract specialists and teachers from other educational institutions. There are also five requirements to consider when creating training courses.

- The student should be motivated to learn, for this it is important that the goals and tasks of education are clearly formulated. At the same time, what is required of the student should correspond to his level of knowledge.

- The presentation of the material should be understandable.

- There should be an opportunity for feedback, including individual feedback.

- It is important to have a system of interim assessment of learning so that the student can have an idea of how well he or she is doing. There are typical problems common to all educational institutions in the organization of distance education. Many teachers, especially humanities teachers, face difficulties in designing and adapting teaching material. Many teachers tend to be conservative, and they strongly oppose such an innovation as distance education. They strongly defend their point of view and defend traditional teaching methods. There are difficulties in selecting the technical personnel who should implement the distance education system and accompany it at all stages. It is important to select qualified people for this role. Distance learning also has certain requirements that students must follow. They are required to be polite and correct in their communication with the teacher and with each other. They should learn not only to speak, but also to write in a good language without mistakes, to formulate their thoughts clearly and clearly. It is very important that students do everything on time and do not abuse the time of the teacher and other children. Finally, they must develop respect for copyright. How effective distance education is in the conditions of Uzbekistan was clearly demonstrated in the pandemic. In particular, due to the pandemic, remote technologies were introduced into the system and 7 million pupils and 500 thousand students were taught online. Of course, due to the fact that the distance education system was implemented in our country for the first time, there were some problems in the organization of distance education in the system. But in a certain sense, this was an experience for Uzbekistan. The reason is that all educational institutions have worked on distance education to a certain extent. At the same time, young people had the opportunity to compare the types of education. In order for distance education to work as well as the traditional education system and give the expected results, it is necessary to change the worldview of students. In this case, the transparent transition of the examination process in distance education, online training courses are mainly aimed at providing basic information, most of them do not provide the necessary qualifications, and are mature in the chosen field without having practical skills. Students should understand that they cannot become experts. In addition, the possibility of achieving the desired results increases when special criteria and standards are developed for the distance education process, and the requirements for classes are fully and perfectly fulfilled. Now in our country, experiments are being conducted by prestigious higher education

institutions on distance learning. Monitoring of processes is being carried out in cooperation with relevant ministries. The most important thing is that regardless of the form of education, training of quality personnel should be the main criterion.

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